

IMPROVING THE MECHANISMS OF DEVELOPING PRACTICAL SKILLS FOR STUDENTS

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Abstract: In the article, the wrestling technique is taught to the students in the course of training. Improvement of the mechanisms of development of practical skills and qualifications of students by the type of wrestling was analyzed.

Key words: Struggle, skill, sports activity, training process, practical development, national values, strengthening, improvement.

INTRODUCTION

The fight, which attracted the attention of millions and gained fame, has its deep historical roots as one of the highest spiritual values of the world .

researches , researches and archeological scientific researches and observations of historians, antiquarians, philosophers and philosophers prove that the age of the struggle is at least 2.5-3 thousand years old. For thousands of years, national sports have been developed and improved in Central Asia. But when our Republic was invaded by Russia, national sports were pushed to the second stage, and Russian sports began to enter its place. But the people never forgot their " big dragon ", "chasing the girl", archery, throwing a javelin and, especially, national wrestling, and constantly improved it. National wrestling is divided into "Fergana wrestling" and "Bukhara wrestling". The Bukhara style of wrestling is similar to European, American and African wrestling with its rules of technical execution . If we take physical exercises as

sports when they were included in the educational programs during the time of the former union, there was no place for national sports. After the independence of our country, development of national sports of the peoples of our republic, including national wrestling, development of laws and regulations of Bukhara and Ferghana wrestling, methodological improvement of its scientific study; great importance was attached to promotion and encouragement , and the involvement of many young people in the struggle.

A number of government decisions were announced in the republic on the restoration of national values , deepening of spiritual and educational knowledge. Introduction to the life of great people such as the great general Amir Temur, the great scholars of the East At-Tirmizi, the national hero Jalaluddin Manguberdi, and the holding of international sports competitions for the President's prize in their name not only attracted the attention of the world public, but also He praised the identity of the Uzbek people to the world.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

The technical training of wrestling is characterized by the level of mastery of the system of actions that ensures the achievement of high sports results by the athlete.

General and special technical training of the wrestler is distinguished. General technical training is aimed at acquiring various movement skills and skills in auxiliary sports, and special technical training is aimed at achieving technical skills in sports wrestling.

Technical training in sports wrestling is aimed at solving a number of complex tasks:

- increase the efficiency of using the maximum voltage;
- save working voltage;

- to increase the speed and accuracy of movement in the changing conditions of competition activities.

Improvement of sports technique is carried out during many years of training of wrestlers, and it is focused on improving technical skills in the chosen type of wrestling.

Technical skill means the perfect mastery of the most reasonable movement technique in the conditions of intense sports competition.

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There are three stages of improving technical skills :

1. Research.
2. Bar q aroration.

3. Improving adaptation.

the first stage , technical training is aimed at forming a new technique of competitive movements , improving the conditions for acquiring it in practice, learning (or re-learning) certain movements included in the system of competitive movements .

the second stage, technical training is aimed at deep mastering and strengthening of all skills of competitive activities .

the third stage , improving the skills formed in technical training, increasing the limits of their variability, consistency , and reliability in accordance with the conditions of the main competitions . involved in expansion .

The main tasks of each technical training phase are :

Achieving high stability and reasonable variability of movement skills that form the basis of wrestling techniques , increasing their effectiveness in competitive conditions .

2. Partial retelling of movement skills , improvement of some parts of the methods taking into account the requirements of the competition activity .

To solve the first task, the method of complicating the external situation , the method of performing exercises in different states of the body is used. To solve the second task - the method of facilitating the conditions of performing technical actions, the method of simultaneous influence is used.

The method of complicating the external situation in performing technical methods is carried out in a number of ways in the house:

1. of conditioned competition helps the athlete to improve the structure and rhythm of performing technical movements, to achieve stability and efficiency faster .

2. Methodical method of preliminary conditions and preparatory actions. For example, when improving a throw, you need to change the distance between the grip and the wrestlers.

3. The method of limiting the space for performing the methods helps to complicate the intended conditions for skill improvement. Small size mats are used in wrestling.

exercises in different conditions of the athlete's body, which makes it difficult to perform technical movements, is also performed in different ways:

the movement in a more complete manner . In this case , after a large volume and intense physical load , the athlete is offered exercises aimed at developing the technique .

Control is a methodical method of performing movements in a state of great emotional stress after training competitions .

suppressing or restricting vision with v q ti-v q ti helps to selectively affect the receptor-analyzer content of motor skills . Forced performance of certain methods or actions in a competitive situation stimulates the wrestler's activity in the process of improving skills. In training matches, the wrestler is instructed to concentrate more on the technical methods of defense, or vice versa, on the methods of attack .

Stages of training The process of training for movement is carried out over a certain period of time. Such a period of time is conditionally divided into three stages: initial learning, partial learning, consolidation and further improvement.

At the initial learning stage, the most important task is to create the imagination necessary for the students to correctly perform the studied action of wrestling. The characteristics of this stage are as follows. Improper distribution of time, lack of precision of movements, uncertainty of muscle tension, presence of excessive movements, violation of the integrity of phases in the performance of technical fighting movements.

In doing so, students spend a lot of extra effort and perform the techniques by straining many of the body muscles. Quick exhaustion and especially lack of work capacity depend on them.

The method of easing the conditions for performing technical actions consists of a number of methodological methods:

1. A methodological method of separating the movement element. For example, in wrestling - to carry out a grab above the waist .

Methodical method of reducing muscular work helps the wrestler to make more precise corrections to certain movements in the skill of movement. In order to improve technical movements, a lighter weight class opponent is chosen for the wrestler .

3. The method of quick information helps to quickly acquire the required width, rhythm, pace of movement, activates the process of understanding the performed movement._

convenient to use a video camera and a video recorder for quick information about the technical activity .

The method of mutual influence is implemented in sports training with the help of methodological methods based on mutual development of physical qualities and improvement of movement skills.

CONCLUSION

It is necessary to create a solid foundation for the successful performance of wrestlers in upcoming competitions .

In students practical skills and qualifications for the type of wrestling improvement through , it is possible to improve the sports skills of wrestlers. The main tasks of the preparatory process are to increase the functional capabilities of the body, improve general physical fitness and develop the physical qualities necessary for a fighter, acquire and improve technical and tactical actions, eliminate shortcomings in their implementation, and educate will and moral qualities . should be

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